

PROF. DR. ISJRIN NOERDIN (1965-1973) SUCCEEDED IN ESTABLISHING THE “MODERN-UNP” FOR THE NEXT DAY

Hendri ¹, Azwar Ananda ², Fitri Eriyanti ³, Siti Fatimah ⁴,
Erianjoni ⁵, and Harisnal Hadi ^{6*}

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: harisnal@fbs.unp.ac.id

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11195617](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195617)

Abstract

This study investigates the educational contributions and breakthroughs made by Prof. Dr. Ir. Isjrin Noerdin, the first Chancellor (Teaching and Education Institute) of IKIP Padang (1965-1973), who used the historical method. Data was collected through a literature study and analyzed using a qualitative approach. The breakthroughs identified include revitalizing the spirit of cooperation among the academic community, relocating campuses, implementing the Semester Credit System, establishing a Labor School & Teacher Training Center, building the Al-Azhar Mosque to strengthen religious values, and awarding an honorary doctorate to Engku Muhammad Sjafe 'i. These innovations have a sustainable impact and continue to be developed by subsequent leaders, especially in strengthening the scientific basis of education. Isjrin Noerdin's extraordinary achievements in improving the education sector made him a leader who should be used as an example and even provided the basis for further honors, such as being awarded the title of National Hero of the Republic of Indonesia.

Keywords: Rector IKIP Padang, Isjrin Noerdin, Breakthrough, Teacher Education, Education Science.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advances in technology and information in the contemporary era have had a significant negative impact on the education sector throughout the world [1; 2]. Research by Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings (QS-WUR) in 2017–2018 evaluated several universities at the global level [3;4;5;6], using survey methods involving the participation of academics, professionals, and campus research [7;8]. The evaluation process is carried out by considering several aspects, including academic reputation, prestige as a leader in the field, publication, and research productivity, and the existence of journals related to higher education [9;10].

In Indonesia, there are 21 Legal Entity State Universities (PTNBH). Some of them utilize data from QS-WUR in the 2020 rankings [11; 12]. Examples include Universitas Gadjah Mada (UGM) ranked 254, Universitas Indonesia (UI) ranked 305, Institut Teknologi Bandung (ITB) ranked 313, Universitas Airlangga (UNAIR) ranked 521, and Institut Pertanian Bogor (IPB) ranked 531. In addition, the government of Indonesia has set an ambitious target to improve PTNBH's ranking of 16 to reach the WUR target cluster in 2024, with a target of ranking 200 for UGM, UI, and ITB, ranking 500 for UNAIR and IPB, and ranking 800 for Universitas Diponegoro (UNDIP). Meanwhile, 10 other universities are expected to achieve a ranking of 1000 or better, including Universitas Negeri Padang (UNP), Universitas Sebelas Maret (UNS), Universitas Sumatera Utara (USU), Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia Bandung (UPI), Universitas Andalas (UNAND), Universitas Hasanuddin (UNHAS), and Universitas Negeri Malang (UM)..

The history of the establishment of higher education in Indonesia reflects the struggle and commitment of national figures as well as community support [13]. Among the universities founded by the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia are (UGM 1949),

(UI 1950), (UM 1954), (UPI 1954), (UNP 1954), (UNAIR 1954), (UNHAS 1956), (UNAND 1956), Padjadjaran University (UNPAD 1957), (USU 1957), (ITB 1959), (UNDIP 1960), Sepuluh Nopember Institute of Technology (ITS 1960), Brawijaya University (UB 1963), (IPB 1963), (UNS 1976), and others [14]. The process of establishing these universities is part of the national effort to strengthen the higher education system in Indonesia [15; 16], which is supported by the thoughts and actions of figures such as Soerkarno, Assaat, Mohammad Hatta, Ali Sastroamidjojo, Mohammad Yamin, Abu Hanifah, Bahder Djohan, Ki Hajar Dewantoro, Sarino Mangunsarkoro, Hamka, Engku Mohammad Sjafe'i, and others. Support from various levels of Indonesian society is key in confirming the existence of higher education as an educational institution that plays an important role in the nation's development.

Several universities mentioned above have an important history as the forerunners of Teacher Education Colleges (PTPG) in Indonesia, including those that were pioneers in the formation of the higher education system in this country. Among these universities, UM, UPI, and UNP succeeded in achieving the highest achievement in Indonesia PTNBH. UNP, as one of the 4,593 best universities recorded, is a clear example of an elite university in Indonesia. Therefore, research into new works and innovative ideas in the field of teacher education and educational science needs to study the history of the founding of higher education. As was done by the first Chancellor (Institute of Teacher Training and Education) IKIP Padang, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin (1965–1973), who played an important role in the establishment of UNP as a modern educational institution at that time.

METHOD

The research method used is a historical research method which consists of four stages, namely Heuristics, Source Criticism, Analysis-Synthesis, and Historiography [17; 18]. Data collection techniques use library research strategies and steps [19; 20]. Data analysis techniques use interactive models while reduction, categorization, synthesis, and hypothesis induction processes [21; 22]. Primary data was obtained through interviews, electronic communication media, focus group discussions (FGD), document analysis, and written sources created by historical actors. Secondary data sources are obtained through interpretations that other people have made of primary sources, historical works written by historians in the form of books, journals, articles, essays, monographs, etc. Techniques for ensuring the validity of data use data source triangulation, inter-researcher triangulation, method triangulation, and theory triangulation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Forerunner of PTPG or Teacher Education College in Indonesia

The forerunner of UNP was PTPG Batusangkar which was founded on 1 September 1954 and opened on 23 October 1954 by the Minister of Education, Teaching and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia (1953-1955), Mr. Muhammad Yamin in 1954. former fort Fort Van der Capellen Batusangkar, an old fort Dutch which was built during the Padri War in Minangkabau (early 1820s). Yamin has a historical explanation for why PTPG was executed in Batusangkar because the city is known as a place rich in cultural heritage and the center of government. Pagaruyung Kingdom from 1347 to

1375 [23]. Prof. Zainuddin Sutan Keradjaan served as the first Dean of PTPG Batusangkar [24].

PTPG Batusangkar became the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education (FKIP-UNAND) in 1956 in accordance with Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation Number 24 of 1956 concerning the Establishment of UNAND in Bukittinggi. FKIP-UNAND was first introduced in Padang around 1958. FKIP-UNAND took place around 1956 – 1963. IKIP Jakarta Padang Branch was established during the transition period of 1964-1965. In accordance with the Decree of the Minister of Higher Education and Science (PTIP) No. 351/1965 dated 7 August 1965, and effective from 30 September 1965, there was a change in the status of IKIP Jakarta Padang Branch (1964 – 1965) to become IKIP Padang Stand Alone in 1965 [24].

Figure 1: Prof. Mr Haji Muhammad Yamin with Ir. Bung Karno (Founding Father of the Republic of Indonesia)

IKIP Padang Stands Alone.

Prof. Isjrin Noerdin who served as the first Chancellor of IKIP Padang in 1965 – 1973 and was a member of the Provisional People's Consultative Assembly of the Republic of Indonesia (member of the MPRS-RI). Before becoming Chancellor of IKIP Padang, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin served as Assistant Chancellor III of ITB. Prof. Isjrin Noerdin was very enthusiastic because he wanted to develop his hometown Minangkabau with the philosophy of "Membangkit Batang Tarandam" so he was willing to become Chancellor of IKIP Padang in 1965. The thing that impressed him until the end of his life was his dedication to "developing IKIP Padang from the beginning".

Collaboration between IKIP Padang and PT. Semen Padang, UNICEF, California Texas Oil Company (US), JD Rockefeller Foundation (received \$10,000, sending visual arts teaching staff to the US in 1971), Malaysian Minister of Youth Thaib Machmud, Mr. DJ Barlaw UNESCO Educational Broadcasting Consultant to review the construction of the IKIP Padang amateur radio transmitter under the leadership of Drs. Aldjufri, and Prof. Dr. PE de Josselin de Jong, Professor of Cultural Anthropology at Leiden University, on April 24 1971 was very interested because Minangkabau society has matrilineal characteristics and a tradition of "merantau".

Prof. Isjrin Noerdin built the IKIP Padang Girls' Dormitory (24 May 1971) which was carried out by students from the Engineering Teaching Faculty (FKT) from the Civil and Architectural Department. On June 25, 1971, an official representative of the

World Bank based in Washington (USA) Noor High School came to IKIP Padang to collect data on physical development projects that had been and were currently underway at IKIP Padang and their equipment.

Prof. Isjrin Noerdin founded the Guidance and Counseling Department at IKIP Padang, the first head of the department was Drs. Prayitno. IKIP Padang also received an offer to announce the Scholarship for Library Science Training Courses in the Netherlands August 1971-May 1972, the pilot project of which was the Koninklijk Instituut voor de Tropen in Amsterdam and funded by the International Technische Hulp of the Dutch Government together with the UI Faculty of Letters, Department of Library Science.

UNP Leader

Broken growth disappears baganti is a Minangkabau proverb that is often used to talk about the birth and development of leadership, as well as the process of leadership perseverance that has been going on since the PTPG Batusangkar-UNP era (1954-2023).

Since its founding until now, UNP has had 14 Deans, Dean Coordinators, and Chancellors who serve as UNP leaders in Minangkabau who alternate naturally due to age, older leaders will hand over leadership to the younger generation. This continues continuously, an intermediary between periods.

Table 1. Leadership since the PTPG Batusangkar-UNP era (1954-2023).

Leadership	Leader
Dean of PTPG Batusangkar (1954) became Dean of FKIP UNAND (1956-1964).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof Zainuddin Sutan Keradjaan (1954- 1956). • Dr. Harsojo (1958-1960). • Prof.dr. A. Roesma (1960-1963) . • Majelis Harian Fakultas (DBD) St.KDM. Pontas Nasution (1962-1963)
	•
Coordinator Dean of IKIP Jakarta Padang Branch (1964-1965).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. RM Eddy Azhary. • Dr. M.Dachnel Kamars.
Rector of IKIP Padang (1965-1999).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Ir. Isjrin Noerdin (1965-1973). • Prof. Jakub Isman (1973-1982). • Prof. H. Djamil Bakar (1982-1991). • Prof. Muhammad Ansyar, Ph.D (1991-1999).
Rector of UNP (1999-present).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Muri Yusuf, M.Pd (1999-2003). • Prof. Dr. Z. Mawardi Effendi, M.Ed (2004-2012). • Prof. Dr. Phil. Yanuar Kiram (2013-2016). • Prof. Ganefri, Ph.D (2016- sekarang) .

Table 1 shows the names of UNP leaders who have made breakthroughs in the fields of teacher education and educational science. He left this novelty as a monumental work which continues to be utilized by the UNP academic community and the general public to this day.

These works and breakthroughs were born of course due to the influence of the educational values they received as children, one of which is the values contained in their culture [25; 26].

Figure 2: Dean of PTPG, Dean of FKIP, IKIP Committee Board, Rector of IKIP, and Rector of UNP

Figure 3: Location of the IKIP Padang Campus in Air Tawar which was under construction on 1 September 1965-31 August 1967

Figure 4: Location of UNP Campus in 2023.

The Chancellor's new work and breakthroughs, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin (1965-1973), here is a summary of the work and new breakthroughs made by the first Rector of IKIP Padang:

- 1) In his first year as Chancellor, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin received full support from the academic community to build his hometown. The hope is that it can inspire prospective teachers who study at IKIP Padang and after graduating become teachers in the community.
- 2) Chancellor Prof. Isjrin Noerdin encouraged the active participation of academics in civic engagement at IKIP Padang and emphasized that those involved in civic engagement must have a real contribution to be able to join IKIP Padang.
- 3) Around 1965, when this school was founded, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin relocated the IKIP Padang campus from Pondok Padang to Air Tawar which is now the UNP campus, Street Prof. Dr. Hamka.
- 4) Rector Prof. Isjrin Noerdin formed the IKIP Padang Advisory Council to oversee the development and expansion of the IKIP Padang campus.
- 5) At that time, the Chancellor Prof. Isjrin Noerdin began to promote the concept of SKS (Semester Credit System, which connects credit, semester, and elective systems). SKS was launched in 1975 by the next Chancellor, Prof. Jakub Isman..
- 6) Implementing a comprehensive curriculum for teaching in Kindergarten Laboratories, Elementary Schools, Middle Schools and appointing leaders of the IKIP Padang Laboratory School (10 November 1970).
- 7) Rector Prof. Isjrin Noerdin initiated, pioneered, and led the Padang IKIP Development School Pilot Project 1973-1974.
- 8) The Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia designated West Sumatra Province as the location for implementing educational activities for the National Education Pilot Project which was implemented in West Sumatra on August 24, 1970, this action aimed to increase the average quality of national education at that time.

- 9) Rector Prof Isjrin Noerdin pioneered and founded the Education Pilot Project in West Sumatra around the 1970s, namely trying out everything related to education. This pilot project by the Chancellor Prof. Isjrin Noerdin was proposed to the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia to become BPG IKIP Padang (Teacher Upgrading Center, TUC). At that time, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin also served as Head of the Regional Office of the Ministry of Education and Culture, West Sumatra. This TUC was successfully realized during the term of the following Rector, namely Prof. Jakub Isman in 1976. This TUC has even become a role model or prototype for various other IKIPs in Indonesia. TUC then became the Education Quality Assurance Institute (EQAI)/Education Quality Assurance Center (EQAC) located within the UNP campus complex..
- 10) Rector Prof Isjrin Noerdin, Hasan Beyk Datuak Marajo, and other community leaders have succeeded in building the Al-Azhar Mosque at the former Surau Tuo location which is between the UNAND campus and IKIP Padang in Air Tawar. Since there are 50 petitions, the current political situation is worrying. This mosque was sponsored by DDII, donors from the Middle East, and Indonesian benefactors, most recently with assistance from the Islamic Development Bank (IDB) in 2016, the Al-Azhar Grand Mosque was rebuilt in a new location on the UNP campus. Based on the Rector report at that time, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin, built the Campus Mosque. The aim was to emphasize the importance of Muslim students' faith and worship.
- 11) The Rector, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin, carried out new construction and renovations that emphasized the fundamental knowledge found at IKIP Padang, especially the teaching and learning sciences practiced by Prof. Isjrin Noerdin through the Labor School and the National Project for the Strengthening of National Education, both of which are located in West Sumatra..

In 1968, IKIP Padang awarded the title Doctor Honoris Causa (Dr. HC) to Engku Muhammad Sjafei'i, National Hero of the Republic of Indonesia, in recognition of his extraordinary achievements in the field of education. Prof. Isjrin Noerdin and Drs. Sutan Zanti Arbi, MA (Assistant Chancellor I of IKIP Padang) sponsored the awarding of the title Dr. HC this time, and Prof. Harun Zain (Governor of West Sumatra)? Engku Muhammad Sjafei'i's educational motto is 1) don't ask for mangoes from the rambutan tree, but make every tree bear sweet fruit, 2) Be yourself, and 3) nature develops into a teacher.

Figure 5: First IKIP Padang lecture room (1965)

Figure 6: From left to right (1) Prof Isjrin Noerdin (Rector of IKIP Padang 1965-1973), (2) Sutan Zanti Arbi (Assistant 1st Rector), (3) Prof Isjrin Noerdin's wife, Telma.

After leaving his position as Chancellor of IKIP Padang in 1973, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin was appointed Governor of West Sumatra. He replaced Prof. Harun Zain who served as governor from 1966 to 1977. However, the governor did not grant this request because he had been committed to education long before that, even before he had a relationship with his mother. their grandmothers and ancestors. Brig. Ir. Haji Azwar Anas served as the next Governor of West Sumatra from 1977 to 1987, even though the previous governor's term of office was shorter (1 January 1977 to 10 October 1977) and PJS was led by Prof. Harun Zain because a period of time is needed to modify the country's basic government program. As an ITB chemistry lecturer, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin recently moved back to Bandung. In 1987, he became friends with Hadi Nur, who at that time served as Dean at FBSS due to his father's influence. Hadi Nur is the son of Prof Nur Anas Djamil. Not only that, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin, who currently serves as a guest lecturer at the University of Malaya, also shows a strong commitment to the field of education. Apart from that, UNP will also hand over Dr. HC to Cambodian Prime Minister Hun Sen in the near future, with a hidden message that Indonesia, a country whose majority population is Muslim, must appreciate Hun Sen's ability to serve as head of state stated while firmly showing consideration for Muslims as a minority population.

Figure 7: Former Rector of IKIP Padang, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin gave alma mater jackets to new students as a sign of officially being accepted as residents of IKIP Padang in 1993.

DISCUSSION

According to cognitive learning theory and behavioristic learning theory, there are several educational principles embedded in Prof. Isjrin Noerdin. These principles became his guide as he took action on new educational endeavors. In particular, these principles are vulnerable to being seriously undermined by the educational principles that the professor acquired during his short but significant tenure in society, the general public, and Minangkabau society. He may be a "bumi son" or native Indonesian who went to school and had mentors since childhood from a clan of Dutch colonial children in Bukittinggi. This is in accordance with the writings of Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406) about good rulers and Ralph W. Tyler (1902-1994), an American education scholar, who both emphasized that people and groups in society are influenced by social and religious processes. Apart from that, social structures are created through social interactions.

Minangkabau philosophy states that "life has a monumental work, death leaves a legacy" and can be understood from new breakthroughs and the works of writers in the field of education to date. Previously, IKIP Padang had not implemented the Semester Credit System (SCS), which had the impact of causing internal inertia at IKIP. At that time, SKS was widely used and developed in many universities in Indonesia. The Teacher Training Center (TTC) or Teacher Improvement Center (EQAI / EQAC) has become a role model for IKIP throughout Indonesia.

Prof. Isjrin Noerdin together with Hasan Beyk Datuak Marajo, Indonesian community leaders and philanthropists, completed the construction of the Al-Azhar Mosque at IKIP Padang. This project was carried out to advance the aqidah and worship of Muslim students. According to Prof. Isjrin Noerdin, expanding the mandate means that UNP must remain focused on the field of teacher education, its field of study is strengthened as stated by Roeland van der Rijst, et al and Mestika Zed regarding the learning paths of university teachers during the era of technological innovation in education. Even though there is an expansion of the mandate or expansion of IKIP's mandate to become a university after the first day of its mandate, this is not true. Therefore, what is currently being studied and applied is the science of education and teaching, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin was the first person at IKIP Padang to announce Dr. HC to Engku Muhammad Sjafei for his extraordinary achievements in the field of education in 1968.

Engku Muhammad Sjafei served as the fourth Minister of Education, Training, and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia in the Syahrir II Cabinet at the time of the Proclamation of the Republic of Indonesia in 1946. He was awarded the title Dr. HC by IKIP Padang in 1968. Ibrahim Marah Sutan and Anduang Chalijah together with Engku Muhammad Sjafei founded INS Kayutanam in Minangkabau in 1926. This institution has a truly groundbreaking educational philosophy and has inspired Indonesia's young generation since time immemorial. According to Prof. Prayitno, the first of the three philosophies in this collection was the one that later became the UNP motto: "Nature develops into a teacher". This philosophy was first conveyed to the IKIP Padang community in 1982.

At the State Palace on November 10, 2000, Engku Muhammad Sjafei announced Bintang Mahaputra Adipradana which was announced at that time by Megawati Soekarnoputri, Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia. IKIP Padang announced the awarding of the title Dr. HC to Engku Muhammad Sjafei in accordance with Law

no. 22 of 1961 concerning Higher Education, Article 10 Paragraph (3): this honor can be given to individuals who based on their realization receive acceptance from outside - special training in the fields of humanities and social sciences from certain universities. Because of Engku Muhammad Sjaf'e's expertise in the field of education, IKIP Padang since its inception was entrusted with the task of achieving the goal of "intelligent national life" in accordance with the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution. It could be said that he is the only Indonesian national school and the nation's national education figure whose materials continue to be used. and developed to date.

"Culture" awarding the title Dr. The HC was then continued by the Chancellor afterward, such as UNP Chancellor Prof. Mawardi Effendi (2004-2012) who awarded the title Dr. HC to Gamawan Fauzi (Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia during the era of President Soesilo Bambang Yudhoyono, 2009-2014) on Friday, March 18, 2011 at the UNP GOR Building for public policy for education. Prof. Syamsul Amar, Prof. Azwar Ananda, MA, and Prof. Mukhaiyar were the promoters of the work..

UNP Rector of Prof. Ganefri (2016-present) who awarded the title Dr. HC to the 5th President of the Republic of Indonesia, Megawati Soekarnoputri on Wednesday, 27 September 2017 because she was considered to have contributed to the world of education during her tenure. term of office, namely "the birth of Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System" in the field of educational politics. The promoters are Prof. Sufyarma Marsidin, Prof. Dasman Lanin, Prof. Ahmad Fauzan, Prof. Harris Effendi Thahar, Prof. Rokhmin Dahuri, Prof. Mestika Zed, and Prof. A. Malik Fadjar (contributor).

Dato' Seri Anwar Ibrahim (now Prime Minister of Malaysia) in the field of political education, is certainly useful as an effort to maintain and strengthen relations between nations in the allied country of Indonesia-Malaysia. The promoters are Dr Fahmi Idris, Prof Sufyarma Marsidin, Prof Irwan Prayitno, Prof Mestika Zed, Prof Ahmad Fauzan, Prof Yenni Rozimela, Prof Dasman Lanin. Dr. HC by UNP to Drs. H. Muhammad Jusuf Kalla (10th and 12th Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia) in the field of Education Quality Assurance.

CONCLUSION

Education and leadership processes in Minangkabau society are processes that occur naturally and are closely related to the cultural values and traditions of that society. One interesting aspect is that there is a rotational change of leaders based on the age factor.

This concept is reflected in the leadership succession process where older leaders will hand over responsibility to the younger generation, who will then naturally take over the leadership role. However, it is important to note that this principle requires further clarification to understand the context and dynamics involved in the process. In addition, the educational values instilled in Minangkabau society, as reflected in cognitive, behavioristic, and sociological learning theories, play an important role in shaping the character and leadership of individuals in the community. For example, Prof. Isjrin Noerdin, a respected figure in Minangkabau society, reflects the cultural influence and educational values he brings to every aspect of his life, both within the family, community, and culture.

Reference

- 1) Akour, M., & Alenezi, M. (2022). Higher education future in the era of digital transformation. *Education Sciences*, 12(11), 784.
- 2) Beri, D., Sudiar, O., Komaini, A., Putra, A., Nelwatri, H., Yusra, A., & Santi, T. D. (2023). Online Learning Process During the New Normal Post COVID-19 in Indonesia: A Case Study at the Universitas Negeri Padang. *Journal of Higher Education Theory & Practice*, 23(16).
- 3) Liu, Z., Moshi, G. J., & Awuor, C. M. (2019). Sustainability and Indicators of Newly Formed World-Class Universities (NFWCUs) between 2010 and 2018: Empirical analysis from the rankings of ARWU, QSWUR and THEWUR. *Sustainability*, 11(10), 2745.
- 4) Estrada-Real, A. C., & Cantu-Ortiz, F. J. (2022). A data analytics approach for university competitiveness: the QS world university rankings. *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJDeM)*, 16(3), 871-891.
- 5) Benito, M., Gil, P., & Romera, R. (2020). Evaluating the influence of country characteristics on the Higher Education System Rankings' progress. *Journal of Informetrics*, 14(3), 101051.
- 6) Hijriyantomi Suyuthie, Ganefri, Asmar Yulastri, Nizwardi Jalinus, Ambiyar, Sukardi, & Alfajri Yusra. (2024). Work Based Learning Model In An Effort To Improve The Competence Of Vocational Student Graduates In Systematic Literature Reviews. *Dalam Community Practitioner* (Vol. 21, Nomor 04, hlm. 441–451). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964820>
- 7) Research by Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings (QS-WUR) in 2017–2018 conducted an evaluation of a number of universities at the global level using a survey method involving the participation of academics, professionals and campus research
- 8) Teixeira, T., & Picinin, C. T. (2024). University Rankings: Proposal for a Future Research Agenda through a Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 16(7), 3043.
- 9) Brika, S. K. M., Algamdi, A., Chergui, K., Musa, A. A., & Zouaghi, R. (2021, May). Quality of higher education: A bibliometric review study. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 6, p. 666087). Frontiers Media SA.
- 10) Lane, J. E., & KINSER, K. (2016). Rankings, higher education internationalisation and national strategies: Tradeoffs, policy levers and (un) intended outcomes. In *Global Rankings and the Geopolitics of Higher Education* (pp. 282-298). Routledge.
- 11) Nasution, V. I. A., Prasajo, E., Jannah, L. M., & Yumitro, G. (2020). Governance of autonomous higher education institution toward world-class university: A case study at the universitas Indonesia. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(10).
- 12) Aisiah, A., Purwati, S., Pernantah, P. S., Afriani, R., & Putri, B. M. (2023). History Students' Readiness in Using QR Code Based E-Job Sheet. *JOIV: International Journal on Informatics Visualization*, 7(4), 2469-2473.
- 13) Pambudi, N. A., & Harjanto, B. (2020). Vocational education in Indonesia: History, development, opportunities, and challenges. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 115, 105092.
- 14) Foray, J. L. (2013). A unified empire of equal parts: The Dutch Commonwealth schemes of the 1920s–40s. *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History*, 41(2), 259-284.
- 15) Moeliodihardjo, B. Y., Soemardi, B. W., Brodjonegoro, S. S., & Hatakenaka, S. (2012). University, industry, and government partnership: Its present and future challenges in Indonesia. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 52, 307-316.
- 16) Moeis, I., Febriani, R., Sandra, I., & Pabbajah, M. (2022). Intercultural values in local wisdom: A global treasure of Minangkabau ethnic in Indonesia. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 9(1), 2116841.
- 17) Chorlay, R., & de Hosson, C. (2016). History of science, epistemology and mathematics education research. In *The Didactics of Mathematics: Approaches and Issues: A Homage to Michèle Artigue* (pp. 155-189). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- 18) Yulfa, A., Syafrina, Y., Saumia, Z., & Naldi, H. (2023). The Changes and Spread of Settlements in Chinese Padang, Indonesia. *The Indonesian Journal of Geography*, 55(2), 264-274.

- 19) Hider, P., & Pymm, B. (2008). Empirical research methods reported in high-profile LIS journal literature. *Library & information science research*, 30(2), 108-114.
- 20) Yefterson, R. B., Syafrina, Y., & Lionar, U. (2023). The Monument of Heroic Events and Students' Historical Imagination in Padang. *Paramita: Historical Studies Journal*, 33(1). 150-162
- 21) Moore, J. H., Gilbert, J. C., Tsai, C. T., Chiang, F. T., Holden, T., Barney, N., & White, B. C. (2006). A flexible computational framework for detecting, characterizing, and interpreting statistical patterns of epistasis in genetic studies of human disease susceptibility. *Journal of theoretical biology*, 241(2), 252-261.
- 22) Karima, E. M., Nurlizawati, N., Firza, F., Abidin, N. F., & Ibrahim, Y. (2024). Reducing Cognitive Bias of Pre-Service History Teachers through Augmented Reality. *JOIV: International Journal on Informatics Visualization*, 8(1), 520-525.
- 23) Fahmi, R. (2020). The conflict of interest about gender paradigm in West Sumatera. *Ar-Raniry: International Journal of Islamic Studies*, 2(1), 49-64.
- 24) Yuliana, V., & Hardi, E. (2021). Z Mawardi Effendi: Perjalanan Karir Seorang Akademisi dan Mantan Rektor Universitas Negeri Padang Dua Periode (1975-2020). *Jurnal Kronologi*, 3(3), 272-285.
- 25) Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2020). From expectancy-value theory to situated expectancy-value theory: A developmental, social cognitive, and sociocultural perspective on motivation. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 61, 101859.
- 26) Erianjoni, Anton Komaini, Alfajri Yusra, Eka Asih Febriani, Muhammad Hidayat, Deski Beri, & Chici Cania Afdani. (2024). A Review Of Literature On Preventive Efforts To Prevent Sexual Violence In Adolescents: Sexuality Education Integrated In Sociology Learning. *Community Practitioner* (Vol. 21, Nomor 04, hlm. 1338–1351). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11076501>.